

Leadership Qualities among Students of Business Studies (with special reference to Jesuit Management schools in Tamilnadu – an analysis)

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Abstract: This research work is geared toward ascertaining leadership perception among Jesuit Management Schools in Tamil Nadu. This is because students during the course of their academic years take managerial courses which include leadership as a topic of discussion in their modules. Also these students at some point in their lives will be leaders or subordinates. Thus, it is important to have an insight into what they think about leadership's importance in emerging development. This study mainly focused on Jesuit Management Schools in Tamil Nadu. The study adopted the quantitative research approach through the multi-stage sampling technique and the data were analyzed through the use of descriptive statistics, chi-square, t-test and anova test. The result showed there is no significant difference between the area of specialization in MBA of the respondents and their overall possession. The analysis indicated a strong significant difference between sex and their overall possession among the respondents. Further, the study found that there is a significant difference between sex and the overall qualities of the respondents. The study also found that there is no significant difference between Area of specialization in MBA of the respondents and their overall Qualities. The study concluded that the leadership quality practices of organizational governance, organizational performance review and social responsibility and ethics student leadership directions are positively and directly influencing the performance results of autonomous management colleges.

Keywords: Leadership, Qualities, and Management schools

Introduction

The Indian scenario in the process of organizational changes has received increasing attention on the subject of quality improvement in educational institutions. At present, the quality improvement program is ensured by the assessment activities of the National Board of Accreditation and ISO

certification. These activities are performed voluntarily by educational institutions and are not made mandatory by government authorities. Moreover, program experts make these assessments on the basis of pre-established guidelines but the contributions of the main stakeholders particularly faculty members and students in these assessment processes are less. The aim of this work is an attempt to establish a self-assessment tool incorporating simple quality constructs and contributions of main stakeholders. As the global economy gathers pace, more governments are realizing that their main assets are their people and that remaining, or becoming, competitive depends increasingly on the development of a highly skilled workforce. This requires trained and committed teachers but they, in turn; need the leadership of highly effective principals and the support of other senior and middle educational managers.

Leadership in educational institutions is widely recognized as having crucial importance for performance. Indeed, it is acknowledged as being second only to classroom teaching in terms of its influence on student learning with the greatest impact found in institutions where students' learning needs are the most acute. There is a wide range of issues relating to supporting and promoting the provision of effective leadership in educational institutions, including those around recruitment, roles and responsibilities, retention, succession planning, governance, continuing professional development and reward.

The way in which successful leaders apply leadership quality practices will be influenced by a number of factors, including their judgments about the conditions for teaching and learning in the institutions, the confidence and experience of their staff members; and the behaviour, aspirations and attainment levels of the students. There is a strong association between leadership quality practices and performance of the educational institutions. Successful leadership quality practices improve students' outcomes through their values, virtues, dispositions, attributes and competencies as well as what they do in terms of the strategies they select and the ways in which they adapt their leadership practices to their unique context in order to achieve the excellent performance.

The field of educational leadership and management is pluralist, with many competing perspectives and an inevitable lack of agreement on the exact nature of the discipline. One key debate has been whether educational leadership is a distinct field or simply a branch of the wider study of management. While education can learn from other settings, educational leadership and management have to be centrally concerned with the purpose or aims of education. These purposes or goals provide the crucial sense of direction to underpin educational institutions management. Unless this link between purpose and management is clear and close, there is a danger of 'managerialism', "a stress on procedures at the expense of educational purpose and values".

The process of deciding on the aims of the organization is at the heart of educational management. In most educational institutions, aims are decided by the principal, often working in association with the senior management team and perhaps also with the governing body. However, educational institutions aims are strongly influenced by pressures from the external environment, and particularly from the expectations of the government, often expressed through legislation or formal policy statements. Educational institutions may be left with the residual task of interpreting external imperatives rather than determining aims on the basis of their own assessment of learner needs. The key issue here is the extent to which educational institutions are able to modify government policy and develop alternative approaches based on institution-level values and vision.

While there is global interest in leadership and management, because of its perceived importance in developing and maintaining successful institutions and education systems, there is much less clarity about which leadership behaviors are most likely to produce the most favorable outcomes. Awareness of alternative approaches is essential to provide a set of tools from which discerning leaders

can choose when facing problems and dealing with day-to-day issues. Hence the student has opted to study on perception of management students towards leadership qualities with special reference to Jesuit management schools in Tamil Nadu.

Review of Literature

The paper entitled on (2015,) "Personality and leadership qualities among college student leader" presented by **Ming Sing Chai** on This research focused on a group of student leaders who have been elected by their peers to hold various positions in societies and clubs in the university setting. Findings showed that student leaders chosen by their peers had very high integrity. Multiple regression results showed Neutral personality dimension was the most significant predictor for the leadership quality of showing concern for others. Open personality dimension was a significant predictor for self-confidence. Similarly, Relational personality dimension was a significant predictor for both charisma and integrity. To a certain extent, personality of leaders influences the leadership qualities that they display readily and some leadership qualities such as charisma need to be further enhanced through leadership training.

J.D. Sharma (2013), in his article 'Leadership Paradigm in banks' explains that as per the observations made by RBI, it will be challenging for the banks to raise additional capital and liquidity to support higher asset expansion and also to comply with Basel III requirements. In addition, inter connectedness of our banking system with global financial system and corporate governance are also challenges which are impossible for a single leader to effectively cope with. So, there is an urgent need for multiple leadership positions within the bank especially at strategic, operational and financial levels. Leadership development programme can enhance the knowledge levels of current and future leaders, especially in the field of corporate governance, leadership roles, strategic planning for growth, value delivery and sustainable profitability.

Nutan Chauhan (2011), in his study changing scenario of Leadership in Insurance Sector: A critical Appraisal of LIC and Bajaj Alliance, attempts to find relationship between Leadership style and Performance of Organisation and the effectiveness of Leadership style on the overall development of employees. On the basis of Weighted Average, Z test and Chi-square test, he concludes that Leadership style followed in the organization significantly affects performance of the organization in a positive manner.

Asha Kaul and Jithesh Kumar K (2011) studied the impact of feminine identity and soft influence tactics on leadership styles, specifically task-oriented and participative. The results show that there is a significant correlation between feminine identity and soft influence tactics which directly impact the leadership styles of men and women. It says that these leadership styles are not gender-specific, but defined by the identity of the leader and the situational requirements.

Alexander Johannas Westerdin (2011) through his work, "Connecting Leadership Styles Leadership in 'The New Way of Working' at ING Bank, Netherlands", points out, in what way managers should adapt their leadership style to positively affect the outcomes of the New Way of Working. Difficulties with leadership due to the increase of the physical distance between employees, and between the manager and employees, can be solved based on trust in both directions. But the social cohesion will be reduced when the distance between employees is increased, leading to a more individualized focus of the employees instead of a focus on the team, which ultimately reduces the engagement and the motivation of the employees. In addition to the professional cohesion of the employees, knowledge sharing does not happen spontaneously when employees do not see each other face to face on a daily basis. So, the manager needs to consciously organize moments (for instance every three months) for employees to share their professional experiences and knowledge, to improve

the social and professional cohesion in the department.

Shilu, Viral.M (2011), in the study “Leadership Style of Dyeing and Printing Industry of Jetpur City” throw light on the different leadership styles being used by owners-managers of saree printing units in Jetpur city. Along with that, emphasis is also laid on the influence of demographic factors such as age, educational qualification, experience and family background on the style of leadership being adopted by the leader. The main objective of this study was to examine different leadership styles of owners-managers while taking decisions concerning different areas of the business units.

M.S.Rao (2010), in his book ‘Spot your leadership Style-Build Your Leadership Brand’ explains various types of leadership styles. They are autocratic, democratic, charismatic, strategic, visionary, empathetic, situational, potential, innovative, versatile, principal centered, thought, authentic, diversity, flexible, smart, quiet, servant, global, great, talent, change, knowledge, Chanakyan / Machiavellian, entrepreneurial, tough, women, value-based leadership styles. Moreover, he points out certain myths and truths in leadership. He also explains leadership branding.

Tanyu Zhang (2010) conducted a questionnaire survey on 439 sales assistants in Sydney, to study the relationship between perceived Leadership style and employee engagement—the moderating role of employee characteristics. On the basis of the study he suggests that employee engagement is associated with an employee perception of leadership style in his superior, negatively, when classical or transactional style is used positively in the case of visionary or organizational leadership.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the perception of Business School students towards leadership qualities with special reference to Jesuit management schools in Tamil Nadu.
2. To identify the demographic factors affecting the perception of qualities of leadership among the Jesuit management Business Schools in Tamil Nadu.
3. To evaluate the option that highlights the extent Jesuit Management Business School students possess the quality of leadership.
4. To identify the factors that explain student level of agreement on qualities of leadership.

Hypotheses

The study analyzed the following hypotheses statements:

1. Association between the area of specialization in MBA of the respondents and their overall possession.
2. Difference between the area of specialization in MBA of the respondents and their overall Possession.
3. Difference between the area of specialization in MBA of the respondents and their overall Qualities.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

a) Type of Research

The research design used for this study is Quantitative and Exploratory research.

Quantitative research emphasizes objective measurements and the statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data collected through polls, questionnaires, and surveys, or by manipulating pre-existing statistical data using computational techniques. Quantitative research focuses on gathering numerical data and generalizing it across groups of people or explaining a particular phenomenon.

Exploratory research is conducted about a research problem when there are few or no earlier studies to refer to. The focus is on gaining insights and familiarity for later investigation or undertaken when problems are in a preliminary stage of the investigation.

b) Universe of the Study

The universe of the study is focused on Jesuit Management Schools around 720 (100%) students studying in this management school were chosen for this study to source the respondents. It has around;

1. Loyola Institute of Business Administration, Chennai.
 2. Joseph Institute of Management, Trichy.
 3. Xavier Institute of Business Administration, Palayamkottai, In Tamil Nadu.
- [240 Students * 3 colleges = 720 Universe)

c) Method of Sampling

For this study the researcher selected the Convenience Non-random sampling method.

Convenience sampling (also known as availability sampling) is a specific type of non-probability sampling method that relies on data collection from population members who are conveniently available to participate in the study. It is a type of sampling where the first available primary data source will be used for the research without additional requirements. In other words, this sampling method involves getting participants wherever you can find them and typically wherever is convenient.

Non-random sampling is a sampling method where some elements of the population have no chance of selection, or where the probability of selection cannot be accurately determined.

d) Selection of Sample

From the total number of people who are studying in this Tamil Nadu.
 150 responses from 720(20% of the Universe 100%).
 [50 students * 3 colleges = 150 Samples]

e) Data Collection

Data were collected both from primary and secondary sources. Primary data were collected from the public people. Well-structured Questionnaire was used for collecting data. The secondary data were collected from policy documents, published reports of similar projects, journals and Ph.D. thesis, journals and online sources.

f) Tools for data analysis

Both qualitative and quantitative data were analyzed in the light of framed objectives. Quantitative data were tabulated and statistically analyzed. Qualitative data were interpreted based on the information collected from the field. Chi-square and ANOVA test were used by the researcher to analyze the hypothesis.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Profile of the respondents

Indicators	Options	No of respondents	Percentage
❖ <i>Age group</i>	22 to 25yrs	110	73.3
	26 to 28yrs	33	22
	Above 29yrs	7	4.7
	Total	150	100
❖ <i>Marital status</i>	Married	32	21.3
	Unmarried	118	78.7
	Total	150	100

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❖ Area of Living	Rural	73	48.7
	Urban	77	51.3
	Total	150	100
❖ Occupation of parent/guardian	Agriculture	45	30
	Business	42	28
	Teacher	30	20
	Employer	30	20
	Others	3	2
	Total	150	100
❖ Area of specialization in MBA	HRM	47	31.3
	Finance	45	30
	Marketing	28	18.7
	Production	28	18.7
	Others	2	1.3
	Total	150	100

Sources: Primary data

Age is the basic parameter that determine behavior. The table shows the information relating to the age group of the respondents. It may be noted that 110 respondents forming 73.3% of the total respondents are 22 to 25yrs age group; 33 respondents forming 22 % of the total respondents are within the 26-28 age group; 7 respondents forming 4.7 % of the total respondents are above the 29 years age group. So it can be concluded that (73.3 %) of the total respondents are within the 21 to 25 age group workers.

It may be ascertained that 32 respondents forming 21.3 % of the total respondents are married and 118 respondents forming 78.7 % of the total respondents are unmarried. So it can be concluded that 118 respondents forming 78.7 % of the total respondents are married.

It may be ascertained that 73 respondents forming 48.7 % of the total respondents are from rural areas and 77 respondents forming 51.3 % of the total respondents are from urban areas. So it can be concluded that 77 respondents forming 51.3 % of the total respondents are from urban areas.

The above table shows the information relating to the occupation of parents/guardians of the respondents. It may be ascertained that 45 respondents forming 30% of the total respondents are in Agriculture; 42 respondents forming 28% of the total respondents are in Business; 30 respondents forming 20% of the total respondents are Teachers as well as 30 respondents forming 20% of the total respondents are Employer and 3 respondents forming 2% of the total respondents are others. So it can be concluded that 45 respondents forming 30% of the total respondents are in Agriculture.

The Table above shows the information relating to the area of specialization in MBA of the respondents. It may be ascertained that 47 respondents forming 31.3 % of the total respondents are HRM; 45 respondents forming 30% of the total respondents are Finance; 28 respondents forming 18.7 % of the total respondents are marketing as well as 28 respondents forming 18.7% of the total respondents are Production and 2 respondents forming 1.3% of the total respondents are others. So it can be concluded that 47 respondents forming 31.3 % of the total respondents are HRM.

Association between Area of specialization in MBA of the respondents and their overall possession

Null hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant association between the area of specialization in MBA and the overall possession of the students.

Area of specialization in MBA	Overall Possession						Statistical inference
	Low		High		Total		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	
HRM	27	26.7%	20	40.8%	47	31.3%	X ² =12.654 Df=4 .013<0.05 Significant
Finance	28	27.7%	17	34.7%	45	30.0%	
Marketing	22	21.8%	6	12.2%	28	18.7%	
Production	24	23.8%	4	8.2%	28	18.7%	
Others	0	.0%	2	4.1%	2	1.3%	
Total	101	100.0%	49	100.0%	150	100.0%	

Sources: Field data

The above table reveals that there is no significant association between the area of specialization in MBA and the overall Possession of the students. Hence, the calculated value is less than the table value (p>0.05). So the research hypothesis (H₁) is accepted and the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected.

Difference between sex and their overall Possession of the respondents

Null hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant difference between sex and the overall possession of the students.

Overall Possession	n	Mean	S.D	t	df	Statistical inference
Male	75	45.87	4.101	-2.288	148	.024<0.05 Significant
Female	75	48.27	8.105			

Sources: Field data

The above table reveals that there is a significant difference between sex and the overall possession of the students. Hence, the calculated value is less than the table value (p<0.05). So the research hypothesis (H₁) is accepted and the null hypothesis (H₀) is rejected.

Difference between sex and their overall Qualities of the respondents

Null hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant difference between sex and the overall qualities of the students.

Qualities	n	Mean	S.D	t	df	Statistical inference
Male	75	50.79	7.377	-5.470	148	.000<0.05 Significant
Female	75	57.33	7.283			

Sources: Field data

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The above table reveals that there is a significant difference between sex and the overall qualities of the students. Hence, the calculated value is less than the table value ($p < 0.05$). So the research hypothesis (H_1) is accepted and the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected.

One way ANOVA difference between area of specialization in MBA of the respondents and their overall Possession

Null hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant difference between the area of specialization in MBA of the respondents and their overall Possession.

ONEWAY - ANOVA

Overall Possession	n	Mean	S.D	SS	Df	MS	Statistical inference
Between Groups				591.781	4	147.945	$f=3.744$ $.006 < 0.05$ Significant
HRM	47	48.45	7.607				
Finance	45	47.18	6.489				
Marketing	28	45.11	4.709				
Production	28	45.61	4.581				
Others	2	60.00	7.071				
Within Groups				5729.552	145	39.514	

Sources: Field data

The above table reveals that there is no significant difference between the area of specialization in MBA of the respondents and their overall possession. Hence, the calculated value is less than the table value ($p = 0.05$). So the research hypothesis (H_1) is accepted and the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected

Oneway ANOVA difference between area of specialization in MBA of the respondents and their overall Qualities

Null hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant difference between the area of specialization in MBA of the respondents and their overall Qualities.

ONEWAY- ANOVA

Qualities	n	Mean	S.D	SS	Df	MS	Statistical inference
Between Groups				268.377	4	67.094	$f=1.047$ $.385 > 0.05$ Not Significant
HRM	47	54.87	8.870				
Finance	45	54.78	7.856				
Marketing	28	52.21	7.455				
Production	28	52.93	7.338				
Others	2	60.50	.707				
Within Groups				9290.083	145	64.070	

Sources: Field data

The above table reveals that there is no significant difference between the area of specialization in MBA of the respondents and their overall Qualities. Hence, the calculated value is greater than the table value ($p=0.05$). So the research hypothesis (H1) is rejected and the null hypothesis (H0) is accepted.

Conclusion

Now-a-days management students expect high quality leadership as well as better job opportunity in society. So, the quality of education, image of the college, responsibility of the institution, recommendations of faculty members and parents, recruitment, the value of the institution, extra curriculum and friendship are the factors affecting the selection of autonomous management colleges by the students. The loyalty to the institution is very high, meritorious students' admission is improving year by year and environment and safety activities are is good are strongly agreed by the students of autonomous (B - school) colleges. The leadership quality practices of organizational governance, organizational performance review and social responsibility and ethics student's leadership directions are positively and directly influencing the performance results of autonomous management colleges.

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